

THERMAL, MECHANICAL AND WATER BARRIER PROPERTIES OF NANOCLAY TREATED SISAL FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY POLYMER COMPOSITES

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1. Abstract

This work is an extension of previously presented work at the Alabama Composites Conference 2010, paper titled “Thermal, Mechanical and Water Barrier Properties of Sisal Fiber Composites”. In the previous work we discussed a new method of sisal fiber surface treatment using combined clays and NaOH, and compared the thermal, mechanical and water barrier properties with untreated and NaOH treated sisal fibers. In this work, clay and NaOH treated sisal fiber was infused in a thermoset epoxy polymer and thermal properties (TGA and DMA), mechanical properties (tensile strength, modulus, flexural and impact strength) and water uptake properties were examined.

Combined NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber shows superior property enhancement over un-treated and NaOH treated sisal fiber composites. Fiber pullout strength, tensile and water uptake properties were enhanced in NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber composites over NaOH and untreated sisal fiber composites. The outcome of this work is discussed in this paper.

2. Introduction

The use of natural fibers as a reinforcement in polymer matrix continues to grow at a steady pace over the last few years. Commonly used natural fibers are sisal, kenaf, hemp, jute and coir based fibers. In many cases the properties of natural fiber reinforced polymer composites is comparable with the properties of glass fiber reinforced polymer composites. Sisal fiber in particular is used widely as reinforcement in polymer composites mainly because it is cultivable and is abundantly available at an affordable cost. Various chemical treatments are used to improve their surface properties, adhesion properties, moisture barrier properties and mechanical properties of sisal fibers. The sisal fiber

is treated with alkaline treatments like NaOH, silane, KMNO₄, dicumyl peroxide (DCP), Sodium alginate, acrylates, etc. In this regard many authors claim that the surface treatment improves the chemical resistance, surface roughness, fiber-matrix interface bonding, mechanical properties (tensile, fracture toughness, impact and flexural properties) of the fibers. Despite this improvement, such chemical treatment of fibers does not fully control the thermal degradation of the fibers during processing and does not influence the water uptake. Sisal fiber reinforced composites are processed using several processing techniques such as extrusion, injection molding, melt-casting, thermoforming, etc. High amount of heat is generated during thermal processes and hence sisal fiber and other natural fiber are more prone to degradation [1-6]. The above mentioned chemical method partially overcomes the thermal degradation problem; however, it does not solve the thermal processing degradation problem.

Further, natural fibers are prone to moisture uptake rendering them unsuitable for many applications. Hence there is a need for a chemical treatment that can solve thermal degradation as well as the water barrier problems. One such option is to use clay treated sisal fibers. In this paper the improvement of sisal fiber properties through surface treatments using combined NaOH and clays are discussed. Montmorillonite (MMT) based clays are the important fillers in the polymer. Such treatment is expected to provide beneficial result because nanoclays are hard ceramic materials and may improve the thermal stability, modulus, hardness, and dimensional stability of fibers [6-10]. Moreover, the clay acts as an impermeable protective layer to moisture environment and therefore retards water uptake in fiber and hence sustain the material property by protecting from moisture environment. Lastly, it is expected that the fiber-matrix interface

properties are enhanced due NaOH presence. NaOH serves as a coupling agent for fibers and MMT clays and helps in holding MMT clays by physical bonding.

3. Experimental Details

3.1 Raw materials

A commercial DGEBA epoxy resin (LR-20) and hardener (LH-28) procured from AMT Composites, Durban-South Africa was used as matrix and the curing agent respectively. Untreated Na based montmorillonite clay was procured from Southern Clay Products Inc, USA supplied under the trade name of Na⁺ Cloisite. Sisal fibre in the form of chopped strand (length 2.5 cm and diameter of varying from 0.1 to 1 mm) was procured from AMT Composites Durban-South Africa and is used as the primary reinforcement. NaOH pellets were purchased from Merck Chemicals South Africa

3.2 Sisal fiber treatment and Composite preparation

3.2.1 NaOH treatment of sisal fiber

40g of NaOH was added to 100 ml distilled water (at 60°C) and agitated using a magnetic stirrer for few minutes and then 5g of sisal fiber was placed into the solution. The fibers was left in the solution for 1 hour and then removed, dried at 60°C for 4 hours. The procedure used for NaOH-clay treatment was similar to NaOH method; however, the only difference was that the equal weight of clay as that of sisal fiber was added into the NaOH solution prior to the addition of fiber. The NaOH-clay solution was vigorously stirred for 30 minutes to disperse the clay in solution before the addition of sisal fiber.

3.2.2 Composite preparation

Sisal fiber-epoxy composites were manufactured using resin casting method. 100 ml of epoxy resin was taken in a beaker and hardener (LH-28) was added to the resin and the solution was mixed well using glass rod. Thereafter sisal fibers were infused in to resin-hardener mixture. These infused samples were allowed to cure at room temperature for 24 hrs. The resin and sisal fiber was kept at equal weight ratio of 50:50 for all experiments.

3.3 Characterization

XRD was performed to evaluate the clay content in the fiber. XRD was performed on MMT clay, untreated sisal fiber, NaOH treated sisal fiber and NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber. XRD was carried out at a scanning rate of 2°/min with CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5401 \text{ \AA}$) operating at 30 kV and 15 mA. Fourier Transform Infra Red (FTIR) (Nicolet) using an Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR) mode in the range of 400-4000cm⁻¹ was carried out on the treated and untreated sisal fibers to study the functional group and phases. JEOL JSM 840A scanning electron microscope (SEM) clubbed with EDAX was carried out to study the surface morphology of fibers. Water uptake of treated and untreated sisal fibers was carried out by placing the fibers in the distilled water medium.

Water uptake was carried out using samples of 2.5 cm X 2.5 cm X 0.3 cm. Three specimens were placed in a distilled water bath medium. All specimens were weighed at regular intervals using electronic balance with an accuracy level of 0.5 mg and samples were dried using tissue paper before weighing. The water content (W_c) in the sample was measured as % weight increase in the sample. W_c was measured until the composite specimen attained equilibrium water uptake content (ie. no further uptake of water in specimen or very minimal uptake). Equation 1 was used to calculate the water content W_c in the composite specimen.

$$W_c = \frac{(W_t - W_o)}{W_o} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_t is the weight of specimen at time t and W_o is the initial weight of the sample before placing in water.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was carried out at the frequency rate of 10 Hz using the Netzsh model under atmospheric conditions and the test specimens size were of 5.5 cm X 1 cm X 0.3 cm. Tensile tests were carried out for composites at room temperature according to ASTM D 3039.

4. Results and Discussion

Figure 1 shows the SEM photograph image of treated and untreated sisal fibers. The surface image of NaOH-clay treated fiber is clearly different from untreated sisal fiber. It can be seen that the treated fiber has a greater surface roughness. This new surface feature in the treated fiber is due to the presence of NaOH and clay particles. FTIR result (Figure 2) shows the presence of clay and sisal fiber functional group in the NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber. To confirm the presence of clay phases in the treated sisal fiber, EDX result shows the presence of Al, Si and Na phases in the treated sisal fiber (Figure 3 and Table 1). To study the amount of clays present in the NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber, a quantitative XRD analysis was performed and the result is shown in Figure 4. The reduced intensity value suggests that the clay content in NaOH-clay treated fiber is less than that of 100% Cloisite MMT clay. The clay content in the treated sisal fiber was measured by taking the fraction of intensity values of treated sisal fiber to that of Cloisite MMT clay, and the clay content is about 20% in the treated sisal fiber. Fiber pull out strength (Table 2) shows higher values in NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber reinforced epoxy composites due to improved fiber-matrix interfacial properties. DMA result shows increased storage modulus and T_g values in NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber than that of untreated and NaOH treated sisal fiber (Figure 5).

Tensile properties of NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber reinforced composites better properties than that of untreated and NaOH treated sisal fiber reinforced composites (Figure 6). Tensile properties of NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber composites shows 49%, 29% and 12% increase in modulus, strength and elongation respectively over untreated sisal fiber composites (Table 3). Water uptake results (Figure 7) shows that equilibrium water uptake reduces from 62.6% for untreated sisal fiber composites to 49.8% for NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber composites. Also NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber composites shows improved tensile and DMA properties even after placing in water medium (Tables 4 & 5).

5. Conclusions

This work is about the development of sisal fiber reinforced epoxy composites that can withstand moisture, thermal and mechanical environments.

This composite was developed by surface treating the sisal fiber using NaOH and MMT based clays. The advantage of this surface treatment method over other treatments is that the clays act as a hard barrier, stiff and thermally stable material that improves the properties of fibers. Due to improved sisal fiber properties, the resultant composite shows improved mechanical (tensile and fiber pull out strength), thermal (DMA) and water barrier properties over untreated sisal fiber composites. The outcome of this result suggest that the NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber composites provide better improvement in water barrier properties and this study can be further extend to other types of natural fibers and matrix material.

Fig. 1. SEM image of (a) untreated and (b) NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber

Fig. 2. FTIR image of (a) clay (b) NaOH-clay treated fiber and (c) untreated fiber

Table 1: Elemental analysis of NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber

Element	Weight %
C	48.73
O	42.90
Na	5.95
Al	0.81
Si	1.27
Others	0.40
Total	100

Fig. 4. XRD patterns of (a) MMT clay, (b) NaOH-clay treated fiber and (c) untreated sisal fiber

Fig.3. EDAX image of NaOH-clay treated sisal fiber

Table 2: Fiber pull out strength of treated and untreated sisal fibers

Material	Pullout strength MPa
Untreated fiber	31
NaOH treated fiber	35
NaOH-clay treated fiber	41

Fig. 5. DMA properties of composites (a) storage modulus and (b) loss modulus

Table 3: Tensile properties of composites

Material	Modulus GPa	Strength MPa	Strain %
Untreated fiber composites	14.8	38	2.5
NaOH treated fiber composites	19.1	46	2.7
NaOH-clay treated fiber composites	22.1	49	2.8

Fig. 6. Tensile stress-strain curves of epoxy-fiber composites

Fig. 7. Water uptake of epoxy-fiber composites

Table 4: Tensile properties of composites after placing in water medium

Material	Modulus GPa	Strength MPa	Strain %
Untreated fiber composites	10.3	32	2.1
NaOH treated fiber composites	17.5	41	2.3
NaOH-clay treated fiber composites	19.3	45	2.6

Table 5: DMA properties of composites before and after placing in water medium

Material	Before water placement		After water placement	
	Tg, °C	Storage modulus, MPa	Tg, °C	Storage modulus, MPa
Untreated fiber composites	55	2950	49	2431
NaOH treated fiber composites	56	3030	51	2540
NaOH-clay treated fiber composites	64	3206	59	2831

6. References

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